

Fig. 1c

Pseudomonas aeruginosa PAO1 + Φ KZ

10, 20, 30 min p.i.

Fig. 1c replicate

Fig. 1d and replicate

d

Fig. 1e

uncropped images

ctrl. ASO 5 min p.i.

chmA ASO 5 min p.i.

ctrl. ASO 30 min p.i.

chmA ASO 30 min p.i.

Fig. 1e replicate for 30 min p.i. time point
ctrl. 30 min p.i.

(Ctrl.)

chmA ASO 30 min p.i.

(ChmA KD)

Fig. 1f

For ctrl. and *phuZ* ASO, uncropped images are shown in the Figure.

Infection with Φ KZ Δ *phuZ*; for imaging we used a 60x objective.

The infection rate with the *phuZ* deletion phage was low due to a low titer.

Other images from the same experiment

For replicates, see **Extended Data Fig. 2a**

Fig. 2a and replicate

For more replicates see **Extended Data Fig. 4a**

Fig. 2b

Fig. 2b replicate

PaLo44

Fig. 2c replicate

Table 1 and Supplementary Table 1

Nuclease screen (plates 1-3 in this order based on grouping)

Large screen (plates 1-9 in this order)

Small screen

ASO Ctrl PHIKZ055 picA PHIKZ068 PHIKZ120 PHIKZ186 RNase HI PHIKZ177 PHIKZ174 PHIKZ144 chmB chmC

replicate 1

replicate 2

anti-ChmA

4 h 5 h 6 h p.i.
 PaLo44 PHIKZ014 PHIKZ014 PHIKZ014
 ASO Ctrl Ctrl Ctrl
 replicate 1

replicate 2

anti-ChmA

Fig. 3a,b

See Supplementary Data Table 3

[GSE269401](#)

Fig. 4a

See Supplementary Data Table 4

[GSE269911](#)

Fig. 4c

ΦKZ ctrl.

ΦKZ155 KD

Φ PA3 ctrl.

gp176 KD

Fig. 4c replicate

ΦKZ ASO ctrl.

ΦKZ ASO ΦKZ155

ΦPA3 ctrl.

gp176 KD

Fig. 4d and Extended Data Fig. 8e

ASO ctrl. empty

ASO ϕ KZ155

ASO ctrl. p ϕ KZ155

ASO Φ KZ155 p Φ KZ155

ASO ctrl. p Φ KZ155CDN

ASO Φ KZ155 p Φ KZ155CDN

Fig. 4d and Extended Data Fig. 8e replicate

ASO ctrl. pempty

ASO ϕ KZ155

ASO ctrl. p ϕ KZ155

ASO Φ KZ155 p Φ KZ155

ASO ctrl. p Φ KZ155CDN

ASO Φ KZ155 p Φ KZ155CDN

Fig. 4e

2.5, 5.0, 7.5, 10, 20 min p.i.

Fig. 4e replicates 2 and 3

Fig. 4f

Fig. 4f replicate

Extended Data Fig. 1c

Extended Data Fig. 1c replicate

Extended Data Fig. 1d replicate 2

Extended Data Fig. 1d replicate 3

Extended Data Fig. 1e

Extended Data Fig. 1f

f

Extended Data Fig. 1g

Extended Data Fig. 1h

Extended Data Fig. 1i

Extended Data Fig. 2a

bold is used in Ext. Data Fig. 2a

p-value was calculated with the Mann-Whitney-U-Test

The infection rate with the *phuz* deletion phage was low due to a low titer.

Extended Data Fig. 2b

Extended Data Fig. 2b replicate

Extended Data Fig. 2c

Extended Data Fig. 2c replicate

Extended Data Fig. 4b

Extended Data Fig. 4b replicate

Extended Data Fig. 4c

PaLo8 ctrl.

PaLo8 ASO *chmA*

PaLo9 ctrl.

PaLo9 ASO *chmA*

PaLo39 ctrl.

PaLo38 ASO *chmA*

PaLo44 ctrl.

PaLo44 ASO *chmA*

Extended Data Fig. 4c replicate
PaLo8 ASO ctrl.

PaLo8 ASO *chmA*

PaLo9 ASO ctrl.

PaLo9 ASO *chmA*

PaLo39 ASO ctrl.

PaLo39 ASO *chmA*

PaLo44 ASO ctrl.

PaLo44 ASO *chmA*

Extended Data Fig. 4d

other irrelevant

JVPNA-79 (Ctrl.), JVPNA-1895 (ASO *chmA*)

Extended Data Fig. 4d replicate

other irrelevant

Extended Data Fig. 4e and replicate

Bacillus subtilis 168 + SPO1 phage

Extended Data Fig. 4f and replicate

Ctrl. ASO JVPNA972

Extended Data Fig. 5

These data represent selected examples from Table 1 and Supplementary Table 1, hence source files are listed with Supplementary Table 1.

Extended Data Fig. 6a

See Fig. 3b

Extended Data Fig. 6b

See Fig. 3b

Extended Data Fig. 6c

See Supplementary Data 3

Extended Data Fig. 6d

see Supplementary Data 3

RAW sequencing reads are deposited at GEO with the identifier GSE269401

Extended Data Fig. 7a-g

see Supplementary Data 4

RAW sequencing reads are deposited at GEO with the identifier GSE269911

Extended Data Fig. 7h

Coverage files are deposited at GEO with the identifier GSE269911

Extended Data Fig. 8a

see Supplementary Data 4

Extended Data Fig. 8c and replicate

replicate 1 and 2

Extended Data Fig. 8d

Extended Data Fig. 8d replicate

Extended Data Fig. 8e

See Fig. 4d

Extended Data Fig. 8f

non infected

infected

Extended Data Fig. 8f replicate
non-infected

infected

Extended Data Fig. 8g

Extended Data Fig. 8g replicate

Extended Data Fig. 8h

For replicate, see Fig. 4f